

Reactivity of Conjugated Systems. Part V. Condensation of Hydroxymethylene Ketones with Cyanoacetamide.

BY CHITTARANJAN BARAT.

The present work is meant to offer further support to the theory postulated in earlier papers of this series, *viz.*, that in a conjugated system, an ethylenic or acetylenic linkage exhibits a greater activity towards a reactive methylene group as contained in cyanoacetamide than a ketonic one. Whereas in the previous works, conjugated systems of the types $R\cdot CH=CH-CR'=O$, (A), and $R\cdot C\equiv C-CR'=O$, (B), have been considered, the system under examination in the present investigation consists of the type $HO-CH=CH-CR=O$, (C), as afforded by hydroxymethylene ketones with the dual object of establishing the mechanisms of their condensation with cyanoacetamide, and of synthesising monosubstituted hydroxypyridines.

A systematic study of these ketones dates from Wallach, (*Annalen*, 1903, 329, 109), and seems to have ended with Sen, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1347) who obtained quinoline derivatives by condensing hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanones* with cyanoacetamide. He started with the idea that the reaction would lead to an *isoquinoline* compound (I), but found that the reaction actually yielded a quinoline derivative (II).

Claisen and his co-workers (*Annalen*, 1894, 281, 331), in describing the constitution of hydroxymethylene camphor suggested

the following three possible structures for hydroxymethylene ketones in general, and,

(III)

(IV)

(V)

Brühl (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1900, **34**, 1), from refractometric determinations, and Federlin (*Annalen*, 1907, **356**, 251) from colorimetric data, decided in favour of structure (III). Taking the structures (III) and (V) into consideration first, and admitting that the reactive methylene group of cyanoacetamide attaches itself to the ethylenic linkage, the reaction may take place according to equation (1) or (2) as the hydroxymethylene ketone reacts in the keto-enol phase (III) or the aldo-enol phase (V):—

(III)

(VI)

(VII)

(V)

(VIII)

(IX)

yielding a cyanopyridone of the type (VII) or (IX) respectively. But since the condensation product between hydroxymethylene acetophenone and cyanoacetamide on hydrolysis yields *2-hydroxy-6-phenylpyridine* (Leben, *Ber.*, 1896, **29**, 1678), the condensation could not have taken place according to equation (2), since (IX) would have given *2-hydroxy-4-phenylpyridine*. Sen's compound too would have

been an *isoquinoline* if hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* had reacted in the aldo-enol phase (V).

But although the structure (V) can be so easily discarded, it is difficult to choose between the keto-enol type (III) and the keto-aldehyde type (IV) as, quite an identical product would have been obtained had the ketone reacted in the latter form, for since the aldehydic group is more active than the ketonic one, the reaction would proceed as follows:

and the condensation product (XI) would still give a *2-hydroxy-6-(R)-pyridine* on hydrolysis. (*)

Wallach (*loc. cit.*) and others have also decided in favour of the keto-enol structure for hydroxymethylene ketones depending on their behaviour with semicarbazide hydrochloride and have suggested the following mechanism underlying their reaction to give rise to, first, an open chain semicarbazone (XII), and then a cyclic semicarbazone (XIII).

* It seems improbable however, that a substance would exist in an unconjugated form (IV) in preference to the conjugated one (III) since many such compounds are known to adjust themselves to a conjugated form from an unconjugated one (*cf.* Fittig, *Annalen*, 1894 283, 47, 269).

The weak point underlying this hypothesis is that there is room for the formation of an open chain semicarbazide derivative (XIV) or (XV) according as the constitution of hydroxymethylene ketone is represented by (III) or (IV). Both (XIV) and (XV) would give rise to the same cyclic carbonamide (XVI) distinct from the carbonamide (XIII).

Another consideration quite different from above has been brought forward by Auwers and others (*Ber.*, 1926, 58, 2072; also *Annalen*, 1927, 452, 182). They have isolated two cyclic carbonamide derivatives (XIII) and (XVI) depending upon whether the reaction centre of a substituted hydrazine, $\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{NHR}$ is the imino or amino hydrogen atom. The assumption here is that the oxymethylene group is the reactive point and not the ketone, which they prove from the isomeric oximinohydrazine derivative. Under the experimental conditions of the present author, only one compound has been isolated. The open chain semicarbazide derivative from hydroxymethylene acetophenone is described by them as melting at 175-76°. This has been corroborated. The cyclic semicarbazone which they obtained in two forms corresponding to (XIII) (m.p. 142-43°) and (XVI) (m.p. 133-34°) was, however, obtained by the present author as melting at 135-37°. He has, therefore, probably had a mixture in his hands which he could not separate. Other open chain hydroxymethylene ketones were similarly treated with semicarbazide hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate in aqueous alcoholic solution. They yielded also the three products (*vide*, experimental) monosemicarbazide, cyclic semicarbazide and a small quantity of disemicarbazide derivative. In no case, however, were the isomeric cyclic carbonamides isolated.

The conclusion from the above is that the form (IV) is inadmissible, as also (V). Hence, in all these cases, the reactivity of the ethylenic linkage in a conjugated system appears to be predominant.*

In the course of the present work, hydroxymethylene ketones have been condensed with cyanoacetamide under different conditions, and the results so far obtained have clearly pointed to the fact that the course of the primary condensation follows according to the scheme (1) given above, and have elucidated several minor complications encountered by previous workers in this direction.

The following hydroxymethylene ketones and their derivatives have been examined in the present investigation are, (1) hydroxymethylene acetophenone, (2) hydroxymethylene *p*-methylacetophenone, (3) hydroxymethylene ethylphenylketone, and (4) hydroxymethylene methylketone. The condensations have been carried out under the following conditions.

(a) The condensation between the free hydroxymethylene ketones and cyanoacetamide has been carried out both with piperidine and sodium ethoxide as the condensing agents, when identical products [3 *cyano-6-(R)-2-pyridones*] are obtained. This latter fact, therefore, disproves the general contention that free hydroxymethylene ketones cannot be subjected to Michael's reaction on account of their acidic properties, and corroborates the hypothesis that Michael's reaction is in fact an ionic reaction (Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 128, 1868), and since the ketones can react in the form of their sodium salts as well, there is no *a priori* reason as to why Michael's reaction could not be applied to free hydroxymethylene ketones.

(b) The acetyl derivatives of these hydroxymethylene ketones have been condensed with cyanoacetamide by Michael's reaction, when, unlike the case with the acetate of hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone*, (*cf.* Sen, *loc. cit.*) where the condensation is attended with the knocking out of the acetoxy group, it is retained, resulting in the formation of 2-*keto-3-cyano-4-acetoxy-6-(R)-2:3:4:5-tetrahydro-pyridines* like the case with arylidene ketones (Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 321). This discrepancy between the actions of the acetates of hydroxymethylene *cycloketones* and of hydroxy-

* In fact it has been known from a *private communication* that a semicarbazone semicarbazide of hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* was isolated by H. K. Sen (thesis for the D.Sc. degree of the London University, 1915) which also supports the enolic constitution (III) of hydroxymethylene ketones in such reaction.

methylene ketones having a straight chain, is undoubtedly due to the difference in their respective stabilities towards alkaline media, as in Michael's reaction. When however, these condensation products, which still retain the character of an ester, are hydrolysed by alcoholic or dilute aqueous potash, they are transformed into the cyanopyridone obtained in the previous experiments. The following equation explains the whole course of reaction.

(c) The amides of these hydroxymethylene ketones formed by the action of aqueous ammonia on them, easily condense with cyanoacetamide both by heating together the two constituents, as well as by Michael's reaction, giving the same cyanopyridone as before. In the latter case however, an intermediate product of an unstable nature (containing ammonia) is formed, which is readily converted into the cyanopyridone on boiling with dilute hydrochloric acid. In both these two above cases the keto-enol phase being fixed, there can be no doubt as regards its mode of reaction.

(d) The cyanopyridones were next hydrolysed by means of fuming hydrochloric acid in the usual way; hydrolysis with 75 p.c. sulphuric acid generally gave the carboxylic acid (XIX), which lost carbon dioxide on heating, and formed the hydroxypyridine, directly obtained by hydrolysis with fuming hydrochloric acid mentioned above. This comparative stability of the carboxylic acids is a characteristic property of these mono substituted pyridones, and must evidently be due to the absence of a substituent in an adjacent carbon atom (*cf.* the cases of disubstituted pyridones described in previous works in this series, Barat, *loc. cit.*, also *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 851). These pyridones exhibit a hydroxylic structure only when the cyano-group is knocked off, as has also been noticed in the case

of disubstituted pyridones. Hence the structure (XXI) has been ascribed to them.

(e) Finally the condensation of these ketones with semicarbazides has been carried out but by Wallach's method as well as by the ordinary method the cyclic semicarbazone is exclusively formed, together with a very small proportion (from 5 to 10 p.c. of the total yield) of a disemicarbazone, the ordinary aqueous alcoholic medium yielded the open chain semicarbazone in the cold, and the cyclic semicarbazone, on being heated on the water-bath. This non-formation of a disemicarbazone in an alkaline (the ordinary) medium justifies the statements made previously regarding the semicarbazide condensations. Both the open chain and the cyclic semicarbazone yielded the pyrazol derivative when hydrolysed by dilute sulphuric acid.

It has further been observed that with lower members of the series, the formation of triacylbenzene derivatives is more noticeable than with the higher ones; thus, it is more marked in the case of hydroxymethylene acetophenone than with hydroxymethylene *p*-methylacetophenone (cf. Benary, Meyer and Charisius, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 109). The formation of a disemicarbazone with semicarbazide also follows this order.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Of the hydroxymethylene derivatives used herein, that of phenylethylketone was the stablest, while that of acetophenone the least so; the other two, having intermediate stability. Accordingly, except in the first case, they were usually preserved as their sodium (or better copper) salt, and was freshly liberated therefrom before use. Hydroxymethylene phenylethylketone could be kept undecomposed in the free condition for a pretty good length of time.

General method.—One molecule of the freshly liberated ketone and one molecule of cyanoacetamide were taken together in the aqueous alcoholic medium, the mixture cooled in ice, and a little piperidine (usually 4—5 c.c. for every tenth gram-molecule of the reactants) was then added with good shaking. The colour of the mixture deepened, and it was first left in the cold for about half an hour, and at room temperature for two to three days. Usually the condensation product separated out as a solid, but some more could be obtained on diluting and acidulating the mixture. The product usually contained a little of the triacylbenzene derivative, which was easily removed with alcohol. The cyanopyridones were freely soluble in alkalis, and strong mineral acids, and was recovered unchanged on dilution and neutralisation. Ferric chloride did not give any coloration with them. They were usually very sparingly soluble in all solvents excepting glacial acetic acid and pyridine.

The condensations by Michael's reaction were carried out in the usual way, only care was taken to keep the temperature low during the addition of the ketone to the sodiocyanoacetamide suspension; the reaction was over in a day's time and the product was separated by means of carbon dioxide after two days. The cyanopyridone so derived was identical with that obtained by the previous method.

The sodium salts of these ketones, when mixed with the molecular proportion of cyanoacetamide in aqueous solution, and treated with the usual quantity of piperidine and left over, gradually deposited the cyanopyridone in a pure form and in a very good yield in a day or two; some more could be isolated by acidulating the mother-liquor. It is interesting to note that no triacylbenzene derivative is formed in this case, even with hydroxymethylene acetophenone. The amides of these ketones were prepared in the following way:—a strong aqueous solution of ammonia was added to the ketone with good shaking till the latter went into a clear solution, it was then left over at room temperature when the amide began to separate as a heavy oil, which solidified partially or completely on allowing the excess of ammonia to evaporate spontaneously. The amide was then extracted by filtration or extraction by chloroform and isolated. It was purified by crystallisation from a mixture of petroleum ether and chloroform. It was condensed with cyanoacetamide by heating together an equimolecular mixture of the two reactants in an oil-bath held at the melting point of the mixture; ammonia was given off vigorously and gradually the melt solidified with the formation of the

cyanopyridone. It was then treated with alcohol and the condensation product being insoluble, it was easily purified from the unreacted materials and some tarry impurities. When condensed with cyanoacetamide by Michael's reaction, an intermediate compound (having a beautiful canary yellow colour) was obtained which had no sharp melting point and gradually lost ammonia on keeping and specially during any attempt at crystallisation. It was therefore converted into the cyanopyridone by boiling with dilute (1:1) hydrochloric acid for about half an hour. The product thus obtained was identical with the specimens obtained by other methods.

The acetyl derivatives of these ketones were best prepared by treating an absolute ethereal suspension of the dry sodium salt of the hydroxymethylene ketone with a slight excess of acetyl chloride, also in absolute ethereal solution, keeping the mixture well cooled in ice. Soon the cream colour of the sodium salt changed into white, with the formation of sodium chloride. The mixture was decomposed by iced water, the acetyl derivative extracted with ether, dried and isolated by evaporating the ethereal solution followed by crystallisation of the solid acetyl derivative from methyl alcohol. It was condensed with cyanoacetamide by Michael's reaction in the usual way, and was isolated best by carbon dioxide after two to three days. This could be easily converted into the original cyanopyridone by boiling with dilute 5-10 p. c. aqueous or alcoholic potash for 15-30 minutes, followed by acidulation of the alkali solution.

When any of the above condensation products were hydrolysed by 75 p.c. sulphuric acid, the carboxylic acid was invariably produced, which slowly liberated CO_2 on prolonged boiling with the sulphuric acid. If hydrolysed with fuming hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube at lower ($120-25^\circ$) temperatures the carboxylic acid is the main product, while at still higher temperatures ($150-60^\circ$) the hydroxypyridine is directly obtained. These carboxylic acids lose CO_2 at their melting points and yield the hydroxypyridines. These latter exhibit characteristic colorations with ferric chloride, dissolve easily in alkalis and in strong acids, and precipitate unchanged on neutralisation or dilution. They do not dissolve in carbonates, and have excellent solubilities, being soluble even in hot water to a certain extent.

With semicarbazide, the open chain semicarbazone was exclusively formed when condensed in the usual aqueous alcoholic

solution in the cold ; if the mixture was kept at the temperature of a boiling water-bath the cyclic semicarbazone was the main product. When however, the condensation was carried out in glacial acetic acid solution according to the method of Wallach (*q.v.*) the cyclic compound, mixed with a little (5—10 p. c.) of the disemicarbazone, characterised by its sparing solubility in the common organic solvents, was obtained.

The pyrazole was obtained when either of the above semicarbazones were boiled under reflux with dilute (about 25 p. c.) sulphuric acid for about 15 minutes when the solid went into complete solution with a brisk evolution of CO_2 . The solution was boiled for a few minutes more and then cooled, filtered and neutralised with ammonia when the pyrazole separated out. This was isolated and crystallised usually from dilute methyl alcohol. It possessed all the properties of a pyrazole and formed well defined hydrochlorides and sulphates, which can be isolated by adding alcohol to a concentrated solution of the base in the corresponding acid; it can be crystallised without any change from dilute alcohol and is extremely soluble in water imparting an acid reaction to the solution, from which the free base separates out on the addition of ammonia or alkalis.

The general methods detailed above have been followed in all the cases cited below. In the portion that follows, therefore, only the characteristic properties of the condensation and other products have been described, the experimental details being the same in all cases have been omitted.

(A) *Condensations with Cyanoacetamide.*

I. *Hydroxymethylene acetophenone.*—The ketone was prepared by the modified method of Bülow and Sicherer (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 3891); and was preserved as its copper salt and was freshly liberated before use.

3-Cyano-6-phenyl-2-pyridone.—The substance was obtained in an yield of about 25 p.c. with the free ketone with piperidine, 40 p.c. by Michael's reaction, and about 60 p.c. by condensing the sodium salt in presence of piperidine. In the first of the above reactions a considerable quantity of symmetrical tribenzoyl benzene (amounting to about 50 p. c.) was formed which could be easily separated by extracting with alcohol in which it was very soluble, while the cyanopyridone was almost insoluble in it. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine yellow needles, m.p. 115° . (Found: C,

83.41; H, 4.83. $C_{27}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 83.09; H, 4.62 per cent.). The cyanopyridone crystallised from pyridine or glacial acetic acid in pale yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 292-93°. (Found: N, 14.47. $C_{12}H_8ON_2$ requires N, 14.28 per cent.).

The *acetate* of the above ketone crystallised in white prismatic needles from methyl alcohol, m.p. 70-72°. It was no longer soluble in alkalis nor gave any coloration with ferric chloride. It was extremely soluble in all solvents excepting petroleum ether and water. It was easily hydrolysed into the original hydroxymethylene ketone on warming with alkalis. (Found: C, 70.05; H, 5.83. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.47; H, 5.26 per cent.). When condensed with cyanoacetamide by Michael's reaction it gave rise to 2-*keto*-3-*cyano*-4-*acetoxy*-6-*phenyl*-2:3:4:5-*tetrahydropyridine*. On boiling with dilute alkalis (and more slowly with dilute acids) it was easily converted into the above described cyanopyridone. It dissolved unchanged in cold alkalis from which it was recovered unchanged on acidulation. It was sparingly soluble in all solvents except pyridine and glacial acetic acid. Crystallised from either of the latter two, it was obtained in short yellow prisms, m.p. 235-36°. (Found: N, 11.15. $C_{14}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.93 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of the condensation products.—When any of the above condensation products were hydrolysed by sulphuric acid, the carboxylic acid, m.p. 300-02° (decomp.) was usually obtained. It crystallised from acetic acid in white felty needles that lost CO_2 on melting and was converted into the hydroxy pyridine. (Found: N, 6.73. $C_{12}H_9O_3N$ requires N, 6.51 per cent.).

6-Phenyl-2-hydroxypyridine.—This was obtained by decomposing the carboxylic acid by heat, or directly by hydrolysing any of the above condensation products by fuming hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube in the usual way. Crystallised from hot water it was obtained in light, cream coloured scales that melted at 195-96°. Its alcoholic solution gave a peculiar brownish red coloration with ferric chloride, and possessed all the properties ascribed to α -phenyl- α' -pyridone by Leben (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 678) who recorded an m.p. of 197° for this compound. (Found: N, 8.40. $C_{11}H_9ON$ requires N, 8.18 per cent.).

II. *Hydroxymethylene p-methylacetophenone*.—This was prepared by the method of Benary, Meyer and Charisius (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 108), and was preserved as the copper or sodium salt, and was freshly liberated therefrom as in the previous case.

3-Cyano-6-p-tolyl-2-pyridone.—The yield of this compound was nearly double that in the previous case, in all the methods of condensation described there. About 10 p.c. of *symmetrical tri-p-toluoylbenzene* was formed and there was very little production of any tarry impurities during all these reactions. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in cream coloured needles, m.p. 157°-58°. (Found: C, 83.12; H, 5.83. $C_{30}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 83.33; H, 5.55 per cent.).

The cyanopyridone resembled its lower homologue in all properties and was crystallised from pyridine or glacial acetic acid in pale yellow needles melting at 297-98°. (Found: N, 13.57. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.).

The *acetate* of the hydroxymethylene ketone resembled that of the previous ketone in all properties and crystallised from methyl alcohol in white prismatic needles, m.p. at 95-96°. (Found: C, 70.81; H, 6.02. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.59; H, 5.88 per cent.).

With cyanoacetamide it gave *2-keto-3-cyano-4-acetoxy-6-p-tolyl-2:3:4:5-tetrahydropyridine*, which resembled the corresponding *6-phenyl* derivative in properties. Crystallised from acetic acid it was obtained in short yellow prisms, m.p. 258-60°. (Found: N, 10.58. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.37 per cent.).

The *amide*, prepared as detailed above, crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether in long yellow needles, m.p. 103°. (Found: N, 8.7. $C_{10}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 8.7 per cent.). When condensed with cyanoacetamide either by heat or by Michael's reaction it gave rise to the cyanopyridone described above in an yield of 60 to 65 p. c.

Hydrolysis of the condensation products.—When hydrolysed by sulphuric acid, all of the above condensation products were converted into the corresponding carboxylic acid, m.p. 288-90° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.93. $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 6.11 per cent.).

6-p-Tolyl-2-hydroxypyridine.—This could be prepared by any of the previously described methods which when crystallised from 40 p. c. alcohol melted at 200°, and responded to all the usual tests. (Found: N, 7.72. $C_{12}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.57 per cent.).

III. *With Hydroxymethylene ethylphenylketone*.—The ketone was prepared according to the method of Claisen and Meyerowitz

(*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 3275). It was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 118-20°.

3-Cyano-5-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone.—The yield of this compound was about 75-80 p. c. even from the free ketone, the sodium salt being very pasty and hygroscopic it could not be employed. No triacylbenzene was formed from this ketone. The cyanopyridone crystallised from glacial acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m.p. 264-65°. (Found: N, 13.04. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.).

The *amide* which separated at first as an oil solidified at length and crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether in yellow needles melting at 182-83°. (Found: N, 8.92. $C_{10}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 8.7 per cent.). It gave the above cyanopyridone under conditions described in the previous case in an yield similar to that with the free ketone.

Hydrolysis of the cyanopyridone: Formation of *2-keto-5-methyl-6-phenylpyridine-3-carboxylic acid*.—This acid was stabler than the two previous ones as it was obtained both by hydrolysis with sulphuric acid as also by fuming hydrochloric acid in sealed tube at comparatively high temperatures. Crystallised from diluted acetic acid it was obtained in white scales melting at 295° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.24. $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 6.11 per cent.).

5-Methyl-6-phenyl-2-hydroxypyridine.—The above lost CO_2 on melting and was converted into the hydroxypyridine. Crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol in white needles, m.p. 200-2°.

It gave a reddish-violet coloration with ferric chloride and responded to the other usual tests. (Found: N, 7.76. $C_{12}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.57 per cent.).

IV. *Hydroxymethylene methylethylketone*.—The ketone was prepared by the method of Benary, Meyer and Charisius, (*loc. cit.*) the yield being very poor.

3-Cyano-6-ethyl-2-pyridone.—The compound was obtained in an yield of about 40 p. c. from the free ketone both by Michael's as well as Knoevenagel's reactions. The sodium salt could not be employed on account of its hygroscopic nature. Here also no triacylbenzene was formed. Crystallised from alcohol it was obtained in short yellow needles melting at 278-80°. But for its greater solubility it resembles its other homologues in all properties. (Found: N, 19.18. $C_8H_8ON_2$ requires N, 18.92 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of the cyanopyridone: Formation of 2 keto-6-ethylpyridine-3-carboxylic acid.—It was obtained by sulphuric acid hydrolysis of the cyanopyridone as in the first two cases. Crystallised from hot water it was obtained in short white prismatic needles, m.p. 300.02°, (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.56. $C_8H_9O_3N$ requires N, 8.38 per cent.).

6-Ethyl-2-hydroxypyridine.—The carboxylic acid described above lost carbon dioxide on melting and formed the hydroxypyridine; it could also be obtained by direct hydrolysis of the cyanopyridine by fuming hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube at 150-60°. It resembled the other hydroxypyridines in property and gave a sherry-red coloration with ferric chloride. It crystallised from hot water in pale yellow needles that melted at 205.06°. (Found: N, 11.61. C_7H_9ON requires N, 11.38 per cent.).

(B). *Condensations with Semicarbazide.*

I. *With Hydroxymethylene acetophenone.*—The open chain semicarbazone was prepared in the usual way. It was readily soluble in most solvents and was crystallised from dilute alcohol in a mass of white felty needles, m.p. 175-76° (decomp.). (Found: N, 20.27. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 20.49 per cent.).

The cyclic semicarbazone was formed by heating the ordinary reaction mixture or by Wallach's method (*loc. cit.*). It was more soluble than the above, and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 135-37°. (Found: N, 22.74. $C_{10}H_9ON_3$ requires N, 22.46 per cent.).

The disemicarbazone which consisted of about 10 p. c. of the total yield, when the condensation was carried out by Wallach's method, was almost insoluble in all solvents and hence could be easily separated from the cyclic semicarbazone, (which was the main product in the above reaction) by digestion with alcohol. Crystallised from hot water it melted at 225° (decomp.) (Awers and Offens found the m.p. to be 238°). (Found: N, 31.87. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_3$ requires N, 32.06 per cent.).

The pyrazole was easily obtained by hydrolysing any one of the monosemicarbazones with 25 p. c. sulphuric acid. It separated first as an oil which finally solidified, on cooling, crystallised from methyl alcohol in fine white needles, m.p. 72-74°. It was extremely soluble in all solvents excepting petroleum ether and water, and possessed all the tests ascribed to such compounds by earlier workers. (Found: N, 19.58. $C_9H_8N_2$ requires N, 19.44 per cent.).

II. *Hydroxymethylene p-methylacetophenone*.—The *open chain semicarbazone* crystallised from acetone in white felty needles melting at 182-84° (decomp.). (Found: N, 18·98. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 19·18 per cent.).

The *cyclic semicarbazone*, obtained as before, crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine white needles, melting at 145-46°. It resembled the previously described compound in properties, and was extremely soluble in the common organic solvents. (Found: N, 21·18. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 20·9 per cent.).

The *disemicarbazone* was obtained in a yield of about 5 p. c. of the total yield when the condensation was carried out in acetic acid solution according to Wallach's method. It resembled its lower homologue in all properties, crystallised from hot water it melted at 218-20° (decomp.). (Found: N, 30·60. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2N_6$ requires N, 30·43 per cent.).

The *pyrazole* compound was obtained as usual by the hydrolysis of either the open chain or the cyclic semicarbazone described above by dilute sulphuric acid. The *sulphate*, could be obtained by adding alcohol to the acid solution, which, on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 190°. (Found: N, 10·54; S, 12·31. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2, H_2SO_4$ requires N, 10·93; S, 12·5 per cent.). The free base obtained as usual by neutralisation of the acid solution with ammonia crystallised from methyl alcohol in fine white needles melting at 87-88°, and resembled the lower homologue in properties. (Found: N, 18·17. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2$ requires N 17·72 per cent.).

III. *Hydroxymethylene ethylphenylketone*.—The *open chain semicarbazone* was obtained when the condensation was carried out in the usual aqueous-alcoholic medium in the cold. Crystallised from alcohol it melted at 220° (decomp.). (Found: N, 18·94. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 19·18 per cent.).

The *cyclic semicarbazone* was obtained in the usual manner, and but for its slightly lesser solubility it resembled the other homologues in its properties. Crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol it was obtained in white prismatic needles, m.p. 124-25°. (Found: N, 21. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 20·89 per cent.). No *disemicarbazone* was formed with this ketone even when the condensation was carried out in acetic acid medium.

The *pyrazole*, prepared in the usual way crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine white needles, m.p. 118-20°. (Found: N, 17·58. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 17·72 per cent.).

In conclusion the author takes pleasure in expressing his grateful thanks to Prof. H. K. Sen, for his keen interest in the present investigation, and for placing all the resources of the laboratory at his disposal.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

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